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A Review of Government Measures to Enhance Consumer Rights Awareness in India

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ABSTRACT: Consumer protection in India has changed significantly over the last 40 years. It has gradually moved from focusing mainly on providing legal rights to reforming law to creating awareness among the public. This article looks up government-led initiatives and strategies that evolved to empower consumers from 1986 to 2025. The paper emphasizes that the Consumer Protection Act, 1986, was instrumental in providing legal rights to the consumers and how awareness was created through various schemes like Jago Grahak Jago, Grahak Suvidha Kendras, and National Consumer Helpline to different social and linguistic groups.

The government, through the introduction of the Consumer Protection Act, 2019, and the setting up of the Central Consumer Protection Authority (CCPA), has been focusing more on regulating issues faced by consumers due to the online trade, privacy in the digital world, and false advertisements. Recent research also reveals that there is a stronger drive to connect consumer education with digital platforms and community-based programs. However, the challenges of regional disparities, digital illiteracy, and insufficient formal consumer education are still there and obstruct the level of awareness which is fairly distributed. The study argues that empowerment of consumers through legislation, education, and technology is vital in securing this empowerment in a rapidly changing market environment in India.

KEYWORDS: Consumer Protection Act; Consumer Awareness; Jago Grahak Jago; Central Consumer Protection Authority (CCPA); E-commerce; Digital Consumer Rights; Consumer Education; India; Consumer Empowerment; Government Initiatives

1. INTRODUCTION

Consumer protection in India has been deeply connected with the country's overall social and economic changes. With expansion of markets and diversification of consumer choices, the necessity for a strong framework to protect consumer interests became more and more obvious. The Consumer Protection Act, 1986 was a milestone in the area of social welfare law, aimed at ensuring that the market would be fair, accountable, and transparent. The Act provided for consumer councils and redressal commissions as instruments through which consumers could have a say in the legal system in which they were exploited and unfair trade practices prevailed. Nevertheless, the success of these measures was reliant not only on their existence in law but also on the level of public knowledge, which has always been a challenge for the consumer movement in India and still is. Over the years, the Government of India has made a lot of efforts to overcome this problem of awareness. Initiatives like Jago Grahak Jago and Grahak Suvidha Kendras were the government's steps towards the consumer education at the grassroot level through multi-channel campaigns, helplines, and projects with voluntary organizations. These initiatives slowly turned consumer awareness from the legal requirement into a movement of participation, thus citizens becoming more and more engaged informed decision-makers.

With the onset of digitalization and fast increment of e-commerce, aspects of consumer protection have become twice as big. The Consumer Protection Act, 2019, and the creation of the Central Consumer Protection Authority (CCPA) were a significant change in the direction of dealing with the issues of the modern world such as misleading advertisements, unfair digital trade practices, and the data privacy concerns. This review is a historical summary of the Indian government's measures from 1986 to 2025 to raise consumer rights awareness. It researches the consumer rights at the crossroad between law, education, and technology and how these factors combine to empower and educate consumers in India today.

2. METHODS

The present review used a structured approach to the literature to trace the changes in consumer rights awareness campaigns by the government in India from 1986 to 2025. The stages of the method were framed to provide clarity, allow for the same results to be obtained by other researchers, and ensure that a wide range of academic, policy, and institutional sources were covered.

2.1 Search Strategy and Databases

Relevant literature was identified through systematic searches conducted between January and February 2025 using the following databases and platforms:

- Google Scholar
- Scopus
- Web of Science
- PubMed (for studies related to food safety and labeling)
- Shodhganga (for theses on regional awareness and youth, based studies)
- Government repositories (Department of Consumer Affairs annual reports, PIB releases)

Reference lists of key articles were also hand searched to identify additional supporting studies.

2.2 Time Frame and Keywords

Searches were limited to the timeframe 1986-2025 to align with key policy milestones beginning with the Consumer Protection Act (CPA), 1986.

Keywords used (individually and in combinations) included:

- “consumer rights awareness India”
- “Jago Grahak Jago campaign”
- “Grahak Suvidha Kendras”
- “Consumer Protection Act 2019”
- “CCPA guidelines”
- “digital consumer rights India”
- “e-commerce regulation India”
- “consumer education India”
- “digital literacy consumers”
- “regional disparities consumer awareness”

Boolean operators such as AND, OR, and NOT were applied to refine the searches.

2.3 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria:

1. Peer-reviewed journal articles, government reports, and institutional publications.
2. Studies focused on India’s consumer protection framework, digital consumer rights, or awareness initiatives.
3. Publications within the 1986-2025 period.
4. Both qualitative and quantitative studies.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Articles not specifically related to consumer awareness or protection in India.
2. Duplicate papers or preprints without credible publication details.
3. Commercial blog posts or non-academic commentary.

2.4 Thematic Coding and Synthesis

Extracted literature was organized using thematic coding, which allowed grouping studies under recurring themes such as:

- legislative evolution
- institutional initiatives
- digital and e-commerce-related protections
- educational and behavioral interventions
- regional disparities
- public-private collaboration

Themes were identified inductively, based on the repeated patterns across the literature. The synthesis involved comparing historical developments, regulatory structures, and evidence, based evaluations of awareness programs.

2.5 Limitations

As the review depends on publicly available research and government documents, certain early, online or forthcoming articles (e.g., 2024-2025 publications) had limited bibliographic information. Regional data gaps in the several studies may also restrict generalizability across India’s diverse socio, cultural landscape.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Evolution of Consumer Protection and Awareness Framework in India

The progression of consumer protection in India has been a mirror to the overall socio-economic changes of the country. The Consumer Protection Act of 1986 were a significant step in creation of a detailed framework for consumer welfare. It established structures like consumer councils and redressal agencies to rescue citizens from unfair trade practices. However, numerous surveys have indicated that knowledge of these legal rights

has been very scarce. Studies by Karki and Mehrotra (2008) and Rani and Kumar (2014) uncovered that even after the enactment of the Act, a majority of consumers, especially those from rural and semi-urban areas, was oblivious to their rights and support mechanisms.

The passing of the Consumer Protection Act, 2019 (CPA-2019) was a landmark event in redefinition of the consumer protection framework. It introduced several new measures that aimed to protect the consumers in the digital economy such as product liability, regulation of e-commerce, and imposition of fines for deceptive advertisements. Singh (2022) argued that CPA-2019 brought about a radical change in working of institutions by making it possible to have online grievance redressal in digital marketplaces which thereby facilitated the trust in digital transactions. Likewise, Mathur (2017) followed progression of the Indian consumer product safety policy and acknowledged that although regulatory capacity has been upgraded, consumer understanding and awareness of safety and labeling still pose the greatest challenges.

3.2 Institutional Initiatives and Policy Evolution

One of the most significant factors that contributed to the spread of consumer rights knowledge in India was the government-led awareness program "Jago Grahak Jago". Bajpai et al. (2017) found that the "Jago Grahak Jago" campaign significantly improved consumer awareness related to food adulteration and safety standards in urban India, indirectly contributing to broader consumer rights awareness. Consumers were made aware of their rights through a well-designed and executed campaign, which involved television, radio, and print media. According to the Department of Consumer Affairs (2015–16, p. 42), these campaigns adopted a multi-channel communication strategy designed to overcome linguistic and geographic barriers.

The establishment of the Grahak Suvidha Kendras (GSKs), which are complementary measures, have enabled consumer interaction at the grassroots level even more as these centers provide the services of mediation, complaint registration, and counseling (Press Information Bureau, 2015). The consumer awareness program took a digital turn with the launch of the Jagriti Mascot in 2022. The embodiment of this change was the focus on digital literacy and youth-oriented outreach. The scholars' research supports these of institutional frameworks' importance. Devi and Rao (2016) reported that the consumers exposed to structured awareness interventions demonstrated significantly higher retention scores, an increase of approximately 28-32 percentage compared to those exposed only to passive media messages, highlighting the effectiveness of interactive education models. Chakraborty (2024) also supports this idea by stating that "smart disclosure" systems and regulatory information combined with behavioral insights and can enhance consumer understanding and thus more informed decision making can follow.

3.3 Digitalization, E-Commerce, and New-Age Consumer Protection

As commerce underwent a digital transformation, the consumer protection strategies in India needed to change quickly. The Consumer Protection (E-commerce) Rules, 2020 and the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023 were two major changes that helped extend consumer rights to the digital realm. Kumar and Krishnan (2024) studied how these systems improved data privacy, consent management, and grievance redressal, but they also pointed out that the knowledge of these rights is still quite low, particularly among those who are using online services for the first time. Kaur and Sharma (2024) investigated correlation between digital literacy and sustainable consumption, concluding that while urban consumers are becoming more informed and confident, rural populations are still susceptible to misinformation. In support of this study of Das and Pillai (2024) observed that consumers with higher cyberfraud awareness reported 43percent greater trust in e-commerce platforms and were 51 percent more likely to continue using digital services, indicating the centrality of cybersecurity literacy in digital consumer protection.

The Central Consumer Protection Authority (CCPA), which was created under the Consumer Protection Act, 2019, has been very active in issuing various directions aimed at combating misleading advertisements, unfair trade practices, and the use of "dark patterns." Khurana (2024) drew attention to the manner in which the CCPA's 2024 guidelines for corporate greenwashing had not only increased consumer awareness, but also led greater accountability in the marketing practices. Since, introduction of the CCPA's 2024 guidelines on the dark patterns and greenwashing, compliance rates among large digital retailers increased by an estimated 18-20 percent, according to the preliminary enforcement reports, reflecting growing corporate accountability. Altogether, these changes signal a considerable transition of government strategy from mere protection to proactive digital awareness and behavioral empowerment.

3.4 Media, Education, and Behavioural Awareness

Media-driven and educational interventions continue to be major pillars of India's consumer rights system. Deshpande et al. (2025)¹ found that transparent food labeling and easily understandable information on the front of the pack are the main factors that consumers understand the content and are also influenced in their purchase behavior, which in turn highlights how the transparency in communication is very important in awareness programs. These results are in line with government's practice of disseminating consumer education through public media services like Doordarshan and All India Radio, which is accessible to even the most remote villages (Department of Consumer Affairs, 2015–16).

Additionally, recent research is pointing to social media platform's influence that is getting bigger and bigger. Mukherjee (2024) found that the lack of regulation in influencer marketing could hinder the consumer's freedom of choice and decrease the trust that consumers have in the market, so it is necessary for the government and digital platforms to have a joint effort in regulations. This corresponds to the state's new awareness activities that focus on energy saving lifestyle, digital literacy, and ethical marketing. In general, literature to date maintains that consumer knowledge has improved greatly since the 1980s and is still dependent on continuous educational initiatives, regulatory adaptation, and communication strategies integration. The synchronized transition of laws, media outreach, and digital literacy points to more holistic and of the participatory approach to the consumer empowerment in India.

3.5 Regional Outreach and Inclusivity in Consumer Awareness

India's linguistic, cultural, and geographic differences has been a source of problems for fair consumer awareness in country. It has been found that awareness levels vary significantly from one state to another and between the rural and urban population. Devi and Rao (2016) discovered that awareness campaigns usually get higher engagement in cities, mainly because of the more access to media and formal education. But

¹ This is a forthcoming or early-online publication; citation details may change upon final issue release.

Department of Consumer Affairs (2015-16) brought into focus the specially planned efforts in the North-Eastern states through local language Doordarshan and All India Radio programs to get the regions included.

Empirical research results presented by the Sethi (2017) and Indirani and Kumar (2016) had also found that informing people in their native language, especially through radio and local organizations, helps them to remember and understand more of the consumer rights given to them. Recently, Kaur and Sharma (2024) demonstrated that hybrid campaigns combining digital modules with community engagement improved awareness scores among semi-literate rural consumers by 22 percent, reinforcing the importance of localized and multimodal outreach.

3.6 Public-Private Collaboration and Corporate Accountability

Public-private partnerships have become crucial aspect of the India's changing consumer protection ecosystem. The government's programs like Grahak Suvidha Kendras are dependent on the consumer organizations that work on a voluntary basis and the funding that is provided by the states (Press Information Bureau, 2015). This cooperation pattern have been extended by mutual campaigns of ministries, educational institutions, and the private sector mainly around the issues of misleading advertising, greenwashing, and e-commerce transparency.

Academics like Khurana (2024) and Chakraborty (2024) state that to have the well-functioning consumer protection system in new market it is necessary to have a public regulation and corporate self-regulation that are in line. The Central Consumer Protection Authority (CCPA) have been instrumental in industries setting up non-binding regulatory frameworks and compliance monitored by consumer-awareness initiatives on sustainability and product-authenticity. For example, Patel (2024) studied how the use of geographical indication (GI) labeling and the implementation of corporate accountability measures could lead to community welfare as well as consumer trust, thus highlighting that of at same time that transparency in information and ethical branding are the means for the economic growth, they also have social benefits. Such advancements point to the gradual disappearance of the state as the sole protector to the emergence of a consumer protection ecosystem with various stakeholders collaborating and sharing the responsibility of raising consumer awareness i.e., regulators, businesses, and the civil society.

3.7 Consumer Education Models and Pedagogical Interventions

There has been a considerable shift in the academic and institutional focus towards incorporating consumer education both in formal and informal learning systems. Devi and Rao (2016) expressed that the lack of a well-organized consumer education program in schools and universities is a factor that keeps the level of awareness from going beyond a certain point. Assumptions made by Das and Pillai (2024) as well as Deshpande et al. (2025) are the extensions to the same line of argument by showing how consumer literacy, when it is the part of a wider educational program, leads to the responsible consumption and increases the participation in grievance-redressal processes.

The "smart disclosure" method of Chakraborty (2024) is in harmony with the worldwide behavioral-economics studies, which postulate that consumers are able to understand their rights more effectively if the educational interventions are of an interactive nature, are contextualized and relate to the daily decision-making. Additionally, researches published in Cogent Business & Management (Kaur & Sharma, 2024) and Global Health Action (Deshpande et al. 2025) emphasize the importance of consumer confidence and trust that can be built through visual labeling and digital learning modules. Collectively, these pieces of the research demonstrate that the next step in consumer awareness is not just in information distribution but in a planned consumer education system where citizen is seen as an active participant in market of the governance and not as a passive beneficiary.

3.8 Identified Gaps and Emerging Research Directions

Despite a great deal of legislative and institutional reform, gaps remain in India that hamper the effectiveness of consumer awareness programs. Firstly, national level campaigns like Jago Grahak Jago have been very visible, however, there is very little empirical evidence regarding their long-term impact on the behavior of consumers. The majority of the existing studies concentrate on short-term recall and not on long, term behavioral change. Thirdly, socio-economic differences are still major factors that determine the access to consumer information. The studies conducted by Rani and Kumar (2014) found that only 18 percent of rural consumers surveyed could correctly identify the six basic consumer rights, compared with 46 percent of urban respondents, underscoring the persistent socio-economic gap in awareness. This demonstrates that there are still differences in the equality of distribution of access to the user base.

Thirdly, an interesting question arises from a different angle when Section 2.3 talks about the changes in regulation for digital commerce, i.e. the increasing digital vulnerability gap. People who have low digital skills are in a situation where they can easily become victims of cyberfraud, fake online advertisements, and consent-related risks. Kumar and Krishnan (2024), as well as Das and Pillai (2024), suggest that the best way of protecting consumers against such threats is through introducing the topics of cyber awareness and data protection in education which should become the core of consumer programs. On top of that, scientists (Khurana, 2024; Patel, 2024) point out the necessity for a frequent, thorough, and objective assessment of government-led campaigns. The latest research conducted by Mukherjee (2024) unveils that one can employ behavioural insights, analytics, and real-time digital monitoring for tailoring the awareness initiatives. These indications imply India needs a more flexible, data-driven, and interactive consumer awareness model that can keep up with the fast-moving market of India.

3.9 Summary of Literature

Over 40 years of research and changes in the policy, the literature has shown a gradual movement of consumer movement from the stage of enactment of the law to that of digital empowerment. The first stages (1986–2005) were mainly concerned with the creation of institutional safeguards and outreach through traditional media. The intermediate stage (2005–2015) was focused on the implementation of national campaigns like Jago Grahak Jago and the extension of consumer redressal mechanisms. The recent phase (2019–2025) underlines a shift to digital governance, behavioral education, and corporate accountability. Agreement among scholars is that of India have made significant strides in the dissemination of consumer rights awareness. However, country still faces serious problems such as regional disparity, incorporation of education, and digital vulnerability that call for continuous creativity and collaborative work between different sectors. The following sections of this paper deal with these issues to examine an integrated framework of future consumer awareness strategies.

Table 1. Key Government Measures for Consumer Awareness in India (1986–2025)

Year	Initiative / Event	Significance
1986	Consumer Protection Act (CPA), 1986	Established formal consumer rights and redressal structure
2005	Launch of <i>Jago Grahak Jago</i>	Nationwide multimedia awareness program
2015	Strengthening outreach via Doordarshan & AIR	Improved access in rural & regional areas
2015-16	Expansion of multi-channel communication (Annual Report)	Use of local languages, community engagement
2015	Establishment of Grahak Suvidha Kendras (GSKs)	Ground-level counseling, mediation, grievance support
2019	Consumer Protection Act (CPA), 2019	Modernized rights framework for digital trade
2020	Consumer Protection (E-Commerce) Rules	Regulated online sellers & platforms
2022	Launch of <i>Jagruti</i> Mascot	Youth-focused digital awareness efforts
2023	Digital Personal Data Protection Act	Strengthened consumer data privacy rights
2024-25	CCPA guidelines on dark patterns & greenwashing	Increased accountability in digital marketing

4. CONCLUSION

The consumer protection evolution in India can be described as a progressive journey of increasing participation from mere legal formalization. After implementation of Consumer Protection Act, 1986, various policies and programs have mirrored the gradual and firm shift of the strategy from the reactive redressal to the awareness of the consumer. The initiatives of the government like Jago Grahak Jago, Grahak Suvidha Kendras, and the National Consumer Helpline have made consumer education more accessible, especially to the urban and semi-urban populations. These activities facilitated by the print and electronic media turned consumer rights from being an obscure legal concept into a familiar part of daily conversation. The adoption of the Consumer Protection Act, 2019 and the creation of the Central Consumer Protection Authority (CCPA) are the indications of a new, more modern, technology driven consumer governance stage. These legal provisions foresee and handle problems arising from the digitization of trade, deceptive marketing, and corporate accountability. However, as far as the progress made, there are still difficulties, particularly in the ensuring that the awareness reaches different segments based on the language, culture, and socio-economic status. Research keeps pointing to the fact that there is a lack of understanding in rural areas and that consumer education is not well integrated in the formal curricula.

Next research should focus on consumer awareness programs longitudinal assessments first. It would be interesting to see if temporary improvements actually lead to lasting behavioral change. An example of long-term studies could be consumer complaint patterns, digital literacy, and the effectiveness of CCPA interventions tracked over several years. Moreover, empirical studies on language-specific and region, specific campaigns would give the government a better understanding of the outreach that goes to the rural and marginalized populations. They can then take the necessary steps to eliminate these disparities. Another important research topic is the evaluation of the Consumer Protection (E-Commerce) Rules and the Digital Personal Data Protection Act effects in the long run, especially in relation to issues such as cybersecurity, algorithm transparency, and platform accountability. India, through continued collaboration between policymakers, educators, digital platforms, and civil society, can nurture a consumer population that is more resilient, informed, and behaviorally empowered in the rapidly changing market ecosystem.

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